

Visual Impairment Study Of Diabetic Retinal Images With Deep Learning

Celine Carmel MJ
PG Scholar
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala, India
celinecarmelmj@mca.ajce.in

Nimmy Francis
Assistant Professor,
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, Kerala, India
nimmyfrancis@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— The most frequent cause for blindness in people of working age in developed countries is diabetic retinopathy. An estimated 93 million people would be impacted. It is regarded that DR has ranked in the first place among disorders harming eye health of human beings. Therefore, early diagnosis and treatment are crucial for persons with DR to avoid blindness. Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) should be detected early in order to reduce blindness risk in diabetics. It is well documented that Deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) approaches enable automatic DR detection through classifying retinal images of patients. According to universal consensus, early detection and treatment can reduce DR patients' blindness rates to 5%. Traditional methods for diagnosing DR primarily rely on medical professionals manually differentiating 2D colour images of the eye fundus. In such cases, a doctor's skills and expertise are very important to the accuracy of the diagnosis. A patient with DR is varied according to their eye stage, We thus propose to examine a DR in this work and graphically visualize the stage of eye. Early warning learning strategy using classification based on CNNs in combination with retinal images performance blending. With this action, we also want to simplify the model and decrease computation cost.

Keywords: CNN, DR, Deep Learning, Image Data, diabetes

I. INTRODUCTION

The eye condition known as diabetic retinopathy (DR) is connected to uncontrolled diabetes. If DR is discovered early enough, the progression of vision impairment can be delayed or prevented. However, this can be challenging because the condition frequently exhibits few symptoms until it is too late for effective therapy. Currently, diagnosing DR involves an in-depth manual examination of digital colour fundus pictures of the retina by a qualified practitioner. By the time human readers submit their reviews, often a day or two later, the delayed results lead to lost follow up, miscommunication, and delayed treatment. By looking for lesions connected to the vascular anomalies brought on by the disease, clinicians can detect DR. Although this strategy works, it has substantial resource requirements. Where there is a high prevalence of diabetes among the local population and DR detection is most necessary, there is frequently a dearth of the necessary knowledge and tools. The infrastructure needed to stop DR-related blindness will get even more inadequate as the number of people with diabetes rises. Long-standing initiatives have used image categorization, pattern recognition, and machine learning to make good progress toward a comprehensive and automated DR screening system. The objective of this challenge is to test the limits of an automated detection method using colour fundus photography, ideally producing models with realistic clinical potential. Given the large number of DR patients, it is important to investigate the automatic classification of retinopathy images for the diagnosis of DR.

II. RELATED WORK

The categorization of retinal or other medical pictures has been the subject of several studies over the past few decades. Traditional machine learning algorithms, such as those based on SVM, KNN, Regression, and others, often need offline feature extraction beforehand.[4]

Machine learning algorithms like decision trees, SVM, or support vector machine, linear regression, etc are used[1]. SVM is a supervised machine learning algorithm commonly used for classification and regression. The decision tree algorithm is another supervised machine learning algorithm where data is continuously divided at each row on certain rules until the final result is generated[2].

Such methods often make use of extremely deep networks and big datasets to achieve great accuracy. However, in the real world, obtaining high-quality labelled datasets for model training is frequently not that simple. Another well-known fact is that manually labelling a dataset is an extremely challenging and error-prone task. These techniques have their own limitations [5]

We thus propose to examine a DR in this work early warning learning strategy using classification based on CNNs in combination with retinal images performance blending. With this action, we also want to simplify the model and decrease computation cost.[3]

III. METHOD OF DETECTION

Uncontrolled diabetes is linked to high blood sugar, blood pressure, cholesterol, and body weight, and it can harm the retina's tiny blood vessels, leading to a condition known as diabetic retinopathy. Loss of vision can be prevented or reduced in diabetic retinopathy's early stages, but as the condition worsens, it gets harder to do so.

Gaussian filtered retina scan pictures are used in the photographs to identify diabetic retinopathy. APTOS 2019 Blindness Detection has the original dataset accessible. These photos have been downsized to 224x224 pixels so that many pre-trained deep learning models may easily utilise them.

Using the given train.csv file, all of the photos have already been stored into the appropriate folders based on the degree/stage of diabetic retinopathy. Five folders contain the corresponding images[3]

o Convolutional Neural Network

Figure 1: Convolutional Neural Network

The two stages of the CNN model's operation are feature extraction and classification.

FEATURE EXTRACTION

The process of extracting information and features from pictures is called feature extraction, and after that process is complete, the images are passed on to the classification phase, where they are categorised according to the problem's target variable.

CLASSIFICATION

The input image is classified into a label using the classification component. This layer links the data that was obtained in the earlier phases and finally identifies the input with the appropriate taxonomy.

A typical CNN model looks like this:

- Input layer
- Convolution layer + Activation function
- Pooling layer
- Fully Connected Layer

INPUT LAYER

Our input image, as the name implies, can be either RGB or Grayscale. Each picture is composed of pixels with values between 0 and 255. Before sending them to the model, we must normalise them, or transform the 0 to 1 range.

An example of an input picture with three channels—RGB and pixel values—and a size of 4*4 is shown below.

Figure 2: Input Layer in CNN

CONVOLUTION LAYER

The filter used to extract or identify the characteristics of our input picture is applied to it in the convolution layer. Multiple filtering operations are performed on the picture to produce a feature map that aids in categorising the input image. Let's use an illustration to better grasp this. We will use a 2D input picture with normalised pixels for simplicity's sake.

POOLING LAYER

Following the convolutional layer, the pooling layer is used to shrink the feature map's size, assisting in the preservation of the input image's key details or features while speeding up computation.

The major or significant portions of the input picture are still there in the lower resolution version of the input that is produced by pooling.

Max Pooling and Average Pooling are the two most popular forms of pooling.

FULLY CONNECTED LAYER

We have completed the Feature Extraction processes up to this point; the next step is Classification. The input picture is classified into a label using the fully connected layer (which is what we have in ANN). This layer links the output layer to the data obtained from the preceding steps—the convolution layer and the pooling layer—and ultimately assigns the input the desired label.

IV. DATA PREPROCESSING

The dataset utilized in this study, Diabetic Retinopathy Detection article is sourced from the Kaggle platform, which includes several tagged images. A doctor has assessed the degree to which 0 to 4 levels of diabetic retinopathy are shown in each photograph. As a result, the image's label will include the DR level that was determined. By virtue of its characteristics

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7961727

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2023, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

Such as 0-No DR, 1-Mild, 2-Moderate, 3-Severe and 4-Proliferative DR.

Figure 3: illustrates 5 retinal images falling into different categories.

avoid the noises in the dataset the images should have to be cleaned before processing. It include several steps

1. Background Removal
2. Image resizing
3. Histogram Equalization
4. Retina image Normalization

Figures of these steps are given below.

Figure 4: Step -1 retina Image Background Removal

Figure 5: Step -3 Histogram Equalization

Figure 6: Step -4 Retina Image Normalization

After all these steps of data processing the trained data set of csv file is created with image name as id_code and the corresponding DR stage value as diagnosis

	A	B
1	id_code	diagnosis
2	000c1434c	2
3	001639a3f	4
4	0024cdabc	1
5	002c2135f	0
6	005b95c2f	0
7	0083ee80f	4
8	0097f532e	0
9	00a86245f	2
10	00b74780c	2
11	00cb6555c	1
12	00cc2b75c	0
13	00e4ddff9	2
14	00f6c1be5	0
15	0104b032c	3

Figure 7: Csv file of trained data set

V. RESULT

Input an image name in the given text box after reading the name it can understand its classification based on the trained data set.

```

dr_seminar.ipynb
Code
plt.title("Diabetic Retinopathy Graph")
plt.show()

elif a==3:
img=severefilenames+'.png'
predict_class(img) #images path folder/image name

#import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
fig = plt.figure()
ax = fig.add_axes([0,0,1,1])
langs = ['No DR', 'Mild', 'Moderate', 'Severe', 'Proliferate DR']
points = [0,0,0,0,0]
ax.bar(langs,points,color = '#ed0000',width = 0.4) #colour in hex code
plt.xlabel("DR Categories")
plt.ylabel("% of DR")
plt.title("Diabetic Retinopathy Graph")
plt.show()

else:
print("Invalid File Name!!!!")
Enter image name:
    
```

Figure 8: Enter an input image name

Classification of the given image data, it will be an retina image with diabetic retinopathy or an image without diabetic retinopathy. If an image of Diabetic Retinopathy it may be of the following stage like Mild, Moderate, Severe, Proliferate
 The dangerous situation is arranged as follows
 No_DR < Mild < Moderate < Severe < Proliferate

If we enter an image name it will produce a result like this, print whether it is DR or NO_DR

Figure 9: Output of the image detecting that the image is Diabetic retinopathy image or non diabetic retinopathy

Figure 10: Diabetic Retinopathy graph

If a graph of diabetic retinopathy must be altered with many phases, each of which indicates whether the state of the eye is serious or not,

VI.CONCLUSION

Uncontrolled diabetes is linked to high blood sugar, blood pressure, cholesterol, and body weight, and it can harm the retina's tiny blood vessels, leading to a condition known as diabetic retinopathy. Loss of vision may be prevented or reduced in the early stages of diabetic retinopathy, but as the condition worsens, it becomes more challenging to do so. In this paper the CNN algorithm detect the diabetic retinopathy and the graph represents the condition of eye, The system doesn't show any human errors and the ophthalmologist can analyse those results and give suggestions to the patient according to their eye stage. Early detection of the diabetic retinopathy and its stage can help to take the needs to prevent blindness

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Shen, G. Wu, and H. Suk, "Deep learning in medical image analysis," *Annu. Rev. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 19, pp. 221–248, Jun. 2017
- [2] H. Thanati, R. J. Chalakkal, and W. H. Abdulla, "On deep learning based algorithms for detection of diabetic retinopathy," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Electron., Inf., Commun. (ICEIC)*, Auckland, New Zealand, Jan. 2019, pp. 1–7.
- [3] Anghu Chen , Bo Yanghi , Jing Lii , And Jilanwu Wang. " An Approach to Detecting Diabetic Retinopathy Based on Integrated Shallow Convolutional Neural Networks" Institute of Computer Science and Engineering, Northwest Normal University, Lanzhou 730070, China
- [4] D. U. N. Qomariah, H. Tjandrasa, and C. Fatichah, "Classification of diabetic retinopathy and normal retinal images using CNN and SVM," in *Proc. 12th Int. Conf. Inf. Commun. Technol. Syst. (ICTS)*, Surabaya, IN, USA, Jul. 2019, pp. 152–157
- [5] Fong, L. Aiello, T. W. Gardner, G. L. King, and R. Klein, "Retinopathy in diabetes," *Diabetes Care*, vol. 27, no. 1, p. 7, 2004